

MARKERS FOR ESTIMATING LEVELS OF SEVERITY OF IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROME

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Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) is a biopsychosocial disease consisting of a set of functional disorders that cannot be explained by organic changes in the intestines. The analysis of modern data on the etiology and pathogenesis of the functional pathology of the digestive tract allows us to comment on the concept of the formation of the disease, which, of course, is not one, but several etiological factors, and these factors, in turn, are not the same, it is related to several pathophysiological mechanisms [1-8]. **The purpose of the study** consists in evaluating the clinical and laboratory severity levels of the disease in the types of irritable bowel syndrome with the predominance of diarrhea and constipation.

Material and methods. The study was conducted in the polyclinic and gastroenterology department of the Bukhara regional multidisciplinary medical center, and 98 patients who were examined with IBS in outpatient conditions were selected. The diagnosis of IBS was made based on IV Rome criteria (2016). The average age of patients is 34.6 ± 0.9 years.

Patients with IBS were divided into two groups: IBS with a predominant diarrhea (IBS-D – 47 patients) and constipation-predominant type (IBS-C – 51 patients).

All patients underwent general blood, general fecal analysis, fecal occult blood test, blood biochemical analysis, intestinal microbiota analysis, cytokine analysis - IL-1 β , IL-4, IL-6, IL-10, α -TNF (Vektor-Best reagents), fecal calprotectin (De medi tec reagents) and cortisol analysis in blood, from instrumental examinations - esophagofibromastroduodenoscopy (FUGINON. FUGI FILM EPX-2500, 2014, Japan; FUGI FILM-EG-530PF, 2014, Japan), colonoscopy (FUGI FILM-EG -530FL, 2014, Japan), ultrasound examination of internal organs (Vivid S-60, 2014, Norway) was performed.

Research results. In order to facilitate the examination and data analysis, a program was developed for the evaluation of symptoms: absence of symptoms 0 points, mild to moderate symptoms - 1 point, severe symptoms - 2 was evaluated with points. The points collected by each patient are based on clinical-laboratory symptoms (abdominal pain, diarrhea, constipation, feeling of abdominal rest, feeling of

incomplete bowel emptying, false stools, mucus discharge, defecation additional increases in time, IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-10, α TNF, cecal calprotectin and blood cortisol) were summarized. Patients with a score of 21-28 were considered to have a severe disease, patients with a score of 10-20 were considered to have a moderate disease, and patients with a score of 1-9 were considered to have a mild disease. In terms of the severity of the clinical course of the disease, when comparing the types with a predominance of diarrhea and constipation, 14.9% of patients with IBS-D and 27.4% of patients with IBS-C had a severe course. condition was recorded ($p < 0.05$).

Summary. Thus, when analyzing the types of irritable bowel syndrome with the predominance of diarrhea and constipation according to clinical and laboratory parameters, the main part of the patients was mild. At the same time, an increase in the amount of inflammatory cytokines and cortisol in the blood also requires an individual approach to the selection of treatment methods.

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